

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE AND INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *Agricultural production works at the present stage of development under the influence of various conditions and factors that determine its stability and effectiveness to varying degrees. At the same time, the issues of improving the processes of development of agricultural organizations aimed at innovation and investment are gaining special importance today. It should be noted that innovative development and investment development lead to dynamic changes in agricultural production and make it possible to adapt agricultural organizations to a changing external environment in the long term, taking into account their social-economic, production-technological and natural - environmental capabilities.*

Keywords: *agriculture, innovative development, invisibility, industry, economic.*

Introduction

Each Agricultural Organization, as an active market entity, must develop its own scientifically based development approaches that take into account the innovative processes taking place in the industry at all levels of management and allow it to respond appropriately to natural changes in agriculture. implementation of the predicted line of economic behavior. At the same time, the most important priorities for the development of agricultural organizations are innovative processes and scientific and technological progress, which make it possible to constantly qualitatively and quantitatively update agricultural production by introducing and applying products that require science in practice. At the same time, the underdevelopment of the innovation sector should predetermine the development of an effective mechanism for the formation of an innovative environment in agriculture, which can increase innovative activity and ensure the economic security of agricultural organizations. A prerequisite for the effective and sustainable development of Agriculture is to invest in them in sufficient quantities. An important task of agricultural policy is to create favorable conditions for increasing the level of investment in agriculture. Investment is the long-term investment of money (capital) in the economy for the purpose of generating income (profit). They reflect creativity, the expansion, reconstruction and Technical re-equipment of the main funds, as well as the change of working capital associated with them. Additionally, investments-obtaining patent intellectual property rights to securities, etc. Investments-are included in the objects of entrepreneurial activity that generate income (profit) or achieve a certain social effect. Investments for economic categories have the following characteristics: it depends on the economic development of industries and agriculture; provides efficient use of resources; risk of return on investment; there is a (usually long-term) temporary (unit of measurement) accuracy between resource consumption and efficiency. Investment activities in agriculture are a set of practical actions of a legal entity, farmer and farmer, citizen and state on the implementation of investments.

Literature analysis and methodology

Many scientific research works have been carried out by Uzbek scientists on trends in the development of entrepreneurship and small business in the agrarian sphere and its improvement. For Example, B.T.Salimov and M.S. The scientific work of the Yusupovs mentions the need to

increase its export potential for the development of farms[9]. E.I. The main assessment of the competitiveness of Agrarian network farms in the scientific article of Ergashev one of the criteria focuses on the level of entrepreneurship as he.S. Mukhitdinova fruit and vegetable products in the conditions of modernization of the economy¹⁰ approaches to innovating the market¹, M.Ch. Murodova has researched issues such as the specifics of the Innovation Organization of agribusiness in the cluster Method². J.E. In the scientific work of Ataev, the features inherent in the leader, taking into account the fact that the organization, efficiency of entrepreneurial activity in the agrarian sphere directly depends on the intellectual, physical, socio-economic thinking potential of the entrepreneur, as well as the characteristics inherent in the farm itself, were considered as factors affecting its activities. It is also worth noting that the implementation of priorities for innovation-oriented development of agricultural organizations should be based on an effectively built mechanism for managing agricultural production and characterized by achieving the necessary development parameters that reflect the results of production.

References And Results .

The main results include: 1. Some theoretical provisions of the concept of" innovation-oriented development of agricultural organizations "were clarified: the concept of" innovation-oriented development of agricultural organizations " is given the author's definition, which is fundamentally different in sequence. a process that allows, under the influence of internal changes and external influences, to create the necessary conditions for qualitative changes in agricultural production in an intensive mode and in accordance with the strategic goals of organizations; the main features of the innovation-oriented development of agricultural organizations are highlighted (this concept is inextricably linked with scientific and technical progress and innovative processes taking as a process of natural renewal, as a result of which the transition to a new, better state of agriculture as a productive - economic system is carried out);

2. An algorithm for managing agricultural organizations in the transition to innovative development was developed, which for the first time consists in determining the stages of formation, implementation and management of innovative development, taking into account production and resource, innovative, innovative development. the intellectual, infrastructural, institutional and consumer potential of agricultural organizations based on the use of a step-by-step analysis of the effectiveness of the management of agricultural organizations is to check the expected results: increase productivity, productivity, improve the quality characteristics of the product, increase efficiency. resources used, profitability and profitability;

3. A methodological approach to the justification of the mechanism for managing the innovative development of agricultural organizations is proposed, which is characterized by the possibility of determining the specifics of development based on the identification of stages, content and subjects of the development of agricultural organizations. An innovative process with a sufficiently long balance between states of equilibrium and imbalance, on the basis of which a multidisciplinary model of innovation is developed.-directed development of agricultural organizations for the first time, including the sectors of environmental impact; production and resource opportunities, socio-economic, production-technological and natural-environmental renewal;

4. The methodology for assessing the level of innovative activity of agricultural organizations has been improved, which differs from those that are valid in that the indicators used are several

integrated into extended blocks: production and marketing, socioeconomic and⁹ financial-investment. Taking into account the maximum capabilities of agricultural organizations in terms of the entire set of selected indicators, for the first time, the classification of agricultural organizations as actively oriented, passively oriented, potentially oriented and conservative in terms of the degree of involvement in the innovation process. -development of a system-specific model of innovative infrastructure development and commercialization of these innovations and economic support for technical, technological, scientific, information, consulting and organizational agricultural production.

The low economic efficiency of agricultural-oriented investments is significantly determined by the factors of the second group. These include: crises, price imbalances, high credit interest rates, interest rates on producers in the village. The state is considering measures to increase investment in production. For example, when calculating income tax, all enterprises have the right to reduce the amount (amount) of taxable income on investments in the production and non-production sectors. It is impossible to improve the efficiency of investment without solving these issues at the state level.

The privilege is granted only when the company's Amor uses the full amount of zoning deductions. At the same time, the benefit should not exceed 50% of the tax amount, in which the actual amount is not taken into account.

Factors affecting investment efficiency

- A. Internal factors
- 1) correct choice of investment object;
- 2) terms of construction and development of the facility;
- 3) complexity of investments;
- 4) concentration of deposits by objects;
- 5) compliance with the Order of the economy;
- 6) specialization of the enterprise, type of production activities;
- 7) production technology and organization;
- 8) Product Marketing;
- 9) cost of products; 626
- 10) labor productivity.
- B. External factors
- 1) interest rates on loans;
- 2) crisis processes;
- 3) the ratio of prices to agricultural and industrial products;
- 4) income tax;
- 5) product demand;
- 6) seasonality of production;
- 7) natural climatic conditions.

Activation of investment activities and increasing economic efficiency will allow the application of preferential capital investments in agriculture. Improving the efficiency of investments in agriculture leads to the solution of the following problems:

- The creation of new jobs in rural areas increases the employment level of young people;
- Local markets will be able to be filled with natural, environmentally friendly agricultural products;
- Increase in production due to export of export products;

- the increase in the number of small producers leads to an increase in the number of taxpayers to the state budget, which leads to an increase in state budget revenues;
- Increased supply of raw materials to industry;
- Instead of imported goods, the products of processing enterprises are consumed, which leads to an increase in Republican foreign exchange reserves.

Conclusion

It is also worth noting that the implementation of priorities for innovation-oriented development of agricultural organizations should be based on an effectively built mechanism for managing agricultural production and characterized by achieving the necessary development parameters that reflect the results of production. implementation of the goals and objectives set before agricultural organizations in the context of factors of changing economic uncertainty. Reflecting the need for innovation-oriented development of agricultural production in modern conditions, as well as the need for invisibility, these situations determine the relevance and significance of the topic.

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